

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DRUG DEPENDENCE, JOB INVOLVEMENT, LIFE ORIENTATION AND JOB PERFORMANCE AMONG STAFF OF FEDERAL ROAD SAFETY CORPS (FRSC)

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Abstract

Many governments worldwide rely heavily on traffic policing programmes to influence driver behaviour and improve road safety. Traffic policing entails detection and deterrence, guidance and persuasion and constitute critical activities of Federal Road Safety Corps whose job performance is essential and considered as significant indicator for traffic offending regulations. However individual and dispositional has been implicated in the poor performance of the corps. This study examines the role of drug dependence, job involvement, life orientation on job performance among staff of Federal Road Safety Corps. The study was a cross-sectional survey design where 400 officers of Road Safety corps within the Ibadan, Oyo State command were sampled in this study. More than half (56.8%) of the respondents were male while 43.3% were female. Four hypotheses were tested using t-test for independence, multiple regression analysis and Pearson correlation at 0.05 level of significance. Results demonstrated that there was significant relationship between job involvement, drug dependence and job performance. While life orientation did not significantly correlate job performance. Job involvement and drug dependence significantly predict job performance [$F(3,396) = 15.04, R^2 = .102; p < .05$]. Gender did not have significant influence on job performance. Further, results show that educational status ($\beta = .25; p < .05$) significantly predict job performance [$F(3,396) = 11.36, R^2 = .079; p < .05$]. Reducing drug related problems among officers and increasing job involvement among employee contributes to job performance and improvement in road traffic offending regulations.

Keywords: *Drug dependence, Job involvement, Life orientation, Job performance, FRSC.*

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Introduction

The world is looking forward to enhance performance in organizations, which would give high job-outcomes to their employees and would also treasure excellence and efficiency. Employees are a back bone of any organization and play a vital role in the success of organization. Owing to this, job performance is one of most essential elements of organizational behavior research that and has been considered as significant indicator for the effective organizations. Further, the success of an organization is dependent on good performance of its employee (Colquitt et al., 2010). Similarly, performance of workers is extremely crucial for any human organisation as it ultimately leads to organisational success (Shaughnessy, 2017). Like other sectors, the road safety sector is also dependent on the good performance of its employees as the quality of the road traffic management and accident prevention process is influenced by officers' job performance. Therefore, effective job performances of officers are essential for improvement of safety management as whole (Yusoff et al., 2013).

The Federal Road Safety Commission (FRSC) Nigeria was established in 1988. The FRSC is the lead agency in Nigeria on road safety administration and management. The statutory functions include: Making the highways safe for motorists and other road users, recommending works and infrastructures to eliminate or minimize accidents on the highways and educating motorists and members of the public on the importance of road discipline on the highways. Indeed, the FRSC has recorded meaningful achievements as an auxiliary road safety management outfit. For one, its officers have been visible and effective at traffic management and accident scenes. It is also believed that in composition, the corps boasts of better-trained and educated personnel than the police force. In fact, the society is more tolerant of and cooperative with the Road Safety corps than the existing paramilitary agencies (The daily Guardian, 2015). No doubt, this helps in the discharge of the duties of the FRSC. Now that the nation is faced with increasing number of road mishap; it seems a logical decision to consolidate on the effectiveness and visibility of the Road Safety corps by expanding both its mandate and apparatus. FRSC is a para-military agency of the Government of the Federal Republic of Nigeria that is commissioned to provide measures against road accidents responsible for high mortality rates in the nation against its citizenry. Officers in the FRSC play leadership role day in day out in their various organization which basically rely on their level or seniority in rank.

In this regard, the main issue as addressed by researchers, e.g. (Borman, 2004; Campbell et al., 1990) is definition of those behaviors of employees which constitute good performance. Traditionally such behaviors are related to the performing of core activities of job (Campbell, 1990) but later on it has been expended to diverge behavioral aspects which are not only related to core activities but also related to activities other than core (Cai & Lin, 2006). In this way job performance include task performance, contextual performance in order to grasp this concept in a holistic way (Motowidlo, 2003). The core activities include procedural and declarative knowledge, ability, experience and technical tasks involved in the job (Cai & Lin, 2006; Griffin et al., 2000). Job performance is an issue that has companies all over the world but also fueled a great deal of research in fields of management, occupational health, and industrial and organizational psychology. Several researchers revealed that, employees are the significant actors in determining the organizational performance. Arulrajah and Opatha, (2012) argued that an organization's performance directly depends on the individuals it employs. Without employees' active participation and commitment improving the organizational performance becomes unrealistic. Thus, organizations are paying a great attention on improving the employees' performance to enrich the organization performance. Several factors such as job attitude have been identified to affect the way and manner in which the officers carry out their duty.

One of these factors; employee substance uses whether or not it occurs on the job is an important management issue, because it can undermine employee health as well as productivity. From a managerial perspective, the specific problems created by substance use may include impaired performance of job-related tasks, accidents or injuries, poor attendance, high employee turnover, and increased health care costs (Frone 1998; Roman & Blum 1995). These outcomes may reduce productivity, increase the costs of doing business and, more generally, impede employers' ability to compete effectively in an increasingly competitive economic environment. People who abuse substances do so at a high personal cost including impairment in personal relationships, occupational and social functioning. The literature on the causes of employee substance use generally takes one of two perspectives. The first perspective views the causes of employee substance use as external to the workplace. In other words, an employee may have a family

history of substance abuse that leaves him or her vulnerable to developing drinking problems, have personality traits reflecting low behavioral self-control that make it difficult to avoid psychoactive substances, or experience social norms and social networks outside work—such as friends who drink heavily—that affect drinking behavior (Ames & Janes 1992; Trice & Sonnenstuhl, 1990). Although external factors clearly influence employee drinking habits, a second perspective views the causes of employee substance use as arising from socio-cultural, personality and organizational influence.

Furthermore, some researchers revealed that, job involvement plays a vital role in determining the job performance of employees. Employee job involvement has been predicted to have a significant impact on numerous organizationally important outcomes (Rotenbery & Moberg, 2007). Thus, organizations seriously focus on improving the job involvement of employees to enhance their job performance. Job involvement is one of the most studied employee attitudes in organizational research. Job involvement has attracted attention as a key contributing factor to an organization's success (Abdallah et al., 2017). Kanungo, (1982a) defined job involvement as the degree to which a person psychologically identifies or committed to his/her job. Job involvement of employees contributes to determining the success and failure of the organizations. Thus, organizations focus on improving the job involvement of the employees to achieve the organizational goals and objectives. In this context, several researchers revealed that job involvement highly contributes to enrich the job performance of employees (Diefendorff et al., 2006; Johari & Yahya, 2016). Kanungo, (1982b) stated that, people who are high in job involvement genuinely care for and are concerned about their work.

Life orientation is an important construct in personality interpretation studies and it has been defined as positive evaluation of life and balance between positive and negative affection. Life orientation, in a holistic approach, is about the relationship of oneself with others and the community. This concept focuses on different aspects of personal growth such as physical, motor, spiritual, emotional, intellectual, social growth. Life orientation causes balanced communication between people and plays an important role in the improvement of the quality of life (Sadeghi et al. 2018). Also, experimental researches have shown that taking an optimistic approach and not having pessimistic orientation towards life help people's emotional adjustment, physical health and wellbeing to be increased. More optimism towards life was found to improve workplace attitude and future working relationships (Sadeghi et al. 2018). In This study extends the role of life orientation looking at its role in employees' job performance.

Statement of the problem

The question of what are the determinants of job performance settings has been pursued for decades. Throughout the years, a variety of constructs and predictors have been posited as determinants of drug dependence, job involvement, life orientation on job performance among staff of FRSC. One of the current challenges of the agency is the increasing road accidents and traffic violations on Nigerian roads. Road accident is a serious problem throughout the world in terms of social, health and economic developments. Authorities in virtually all countries of the world are concerned about the growth in the number of people killed and seriously injured on their roads. Furthermore, the rate of mortality in road traffic accident is very high among children and young adults in their prime and who constitute the work force in many countries (Peden et al., 2004; W.H.O, 2004; Sanger, 2010; Anthony-Albanese, 2010). According to Oyeyemi (2003), the frequent accidents experienced on roads and highways in Nigeria over the past years have caused many problems for the development of the country and the carnage arising from it has become the bane of the country's socio-economic development.

Looking at these problem several strategies have been used and are still being used by the FRSC officers to educate road users in general and drivers in particular on the rules guiding road usage and the consequences of flagrant disobedience of traffic rules and regulations. However, many still regards the FRSC as not doing enough due to increasing poor performance among the officers. This bane of poor performance is placed on the pedestal of individual and contextual factors affecting the role of the FRSC officers (Borman & Motiwildo, 2004). Though the proposition that contextual and individual factors are determinant of job performance has sometimes been viewed with skepticism. Highly motivated and well-trained human resources provide the only assurance that any organization will be effective in accomplishing its goals. Based on these, there is need to investigate the influence drug dependence, job involvement, life orientation

on job performance among staff of FRSC. In this sense, the study seeks to examine drug dependence, job involvement, life orientation on job performance among staff of FRSC. While, the specific objectives are as follows:

- 1) To determine the significant relationship among drug dependence, job involvement, life orientation, and job performance of FRSC officers and men under the Oyo State command.
- 2) To assess the joint and independent prediction of drug dependence, job involvement, and life orientation will jointly and independently predict job performance of FRSC officers and men under the Oyo State command.
- 3) To investigate the degree of gender difference on job performance of FRSC officers and men under the Oyo State command.
- 4) To evaluate the joint and independent prediction of age, years of experience, and educational qualification on job performance among FRSC officers and men under the Oyo State command.

Hypotheses

Based on the reviewed of literature, the following hypotheses were generated:

- 1) There will be significant relationship among drug dependence, job involvement, life orientation and job performance of FRSC officers and under the Oyo State command.
- 2) Drug dependence, job involvement, and life orientation will jointly and independently predict job performance of FRSC officers and men under the Oyo State command.
- 3) Female officers will significantly report higher job performance than male FRSC officers and men under the Oyo State command.
- 4) Age, years of experience, and educational qualification will jointly and independently predict job performance among FRSC officers and men under the Oyo State command.

Literature review

Drug Dependence and Job Performance

Relationship between drug dependence and job attitude abounds in many literatures. In a previous study, Kortum (2007) examined work-related stress and psychosocial risks in developing and newly industrialized countries. Findings supported association between stress and substance use/drug abuse, among other factors, with applicability of results beyond a specific sample of workers from Sub-Saharan Africa. Hellriegel et al., (2001) identified higher substance use and other drug abuses, and impulsive behavior as possible behavioral outcomes of the high level of work stress among workers in both Western and developed countries.

Most recently, a cross-sectional study by Frone (2000) based on a sample of 2790 workers from the National Survey of Workplace Health and Safety (U.S.) (response rate 57%), explored the relations of 2 work stressors (work overload and job insecurity) to employee alcohol use. The results fail to support a relation between work stressors and the overall measures of alcohol use, but the results support a relation between work stressors and alcohol use during the workday and after work (Occup Environ Med, 2004). In a study on substance use by doctors during practical training, in which 431 persons (response rate 51%) provided information, the alcohol consumption of 13% was problematical according to the CAGE test. This group also more often reported that their psychological state was poor or moderate (Occup Environ Med, 2004).

Frone (2008) explored the relations of 2 work stressors (work overload and job insecurity) to employee alcohol use and illicit drug use. Consistent with past research, the results fail to support a relation between work stressors and overall measures of alcohol and illicit drug use. However, the results support the relation of work stressors to alcohol and illicit drug use before work, during the workday, and after work. Albar Marin and Garcia-Ramirez (2005) in their study examined the effect of social support on job stress and emotional exhaustion among hospital nursing staff in serville, south of Spain. They found that social support had significant buffering effect on the level of stress and emotional exhaustion experienced by the nurses at work. Nurses that received high kin support, and high levels of co-workers and supervisors support experienced low level of job stress and emotional exhaustion than those who did not. Olaleye (2002) in her study among nurses working in government (state-owned) hospitals found that job stress and burnout syndrome had greater effect on their health and coping ability at work. Cheng and Kawachi (2002) in their study among female registered nurses in America, examined the association between psychosocial characteristics and health functioning. They found that examined separately, low job control, high job

demands and low work-related social support were associated with poor health status at baseline as well as greater functional decline over the four year follow up period. When examined jointly, they found that those with low job control, high job demands and low work related social support had the greatest functional declines. They concluded that adverse psychosocial work conditions are important predictors of poor functional status and its declines over time.

Life orientation and Job performance

Positive Orientation towards work is widely recognized that positive stable personal characteristics are related to job performance (Cameron & Caza 2004). For example, positive psychological traits such as self-esteem, optimism, and life satisfaction are known as significant predictors of job performance (Kluemper et al. 2009; Wright & Cropanzano, 2000).

In an empirical study, Alessandri et al. (2012) used three different samples to demonstrate that, after controlling for P-OR, the influence of self-esteem, life satisfaction, and optimism on job performance was reduced to zero. Across three studies, the mean correlation of Positive life orientation with job performance exceeded .20, and was close in size to that reported for conscientiousness and job performance (see Alessandri et al. 2012c). Furthermore, the influence of Positive life orientation on job performance also held when (1) core self-evaluations (2) positive affect and (3) the Big Five personality traits (McCrae & Costa 2008) were simultaneously taken into account (Alessandri et al. 2012c). These results corroborate the adaptive value of Positive life orientation, defined as the dispositional, genetically-based common core underlying self-esteem, life satisfaction, and optimism, also within work settings (Caprara et al. 2009).

Job Involvement and Job Performance

Lassk et al. (2001) argued that occupation-specific measures of job involvement should be created, and developed a measure of “salesperson job involvement”. Their study uncovered a significant, positive relationship between one facet of their measure, “relationship” involvement, and performance. Also attempting to answer this question, Diefendorff et al. (2002) noted that many previous studies had been conducted using either Lodahl and Kejner’s (1965) or Kanungo’s (1982) job involvement scales, which are contaminated by extraneous constructs (e.g. Kanungo, 1982; Paullay et al., 1994). Diefendorff et al. asserted that the positive effect of job involvement on job performance might be found if a more construct valid measure of job involvement were employed. Using a measure created by Paullay et al. to differentiate job involvement from work centrality, Diefendorff et al. Assessing the impact of job involvement uncovered a small but significant correlation between job involvement and supervisor rated, in-role job performance. In addition, Langfred & Moye, (2004) proposed that job involvement is associated with job autonomy because it provides a sense of belongingness, trust and support which is necessary for high quality relationship in performing jobs.

Methods

Study Design

A cross-sectional survey design was adopted for this research. This type of design occurs where data are gathered at one point in time, in order to answer research questions (Sekaran 2003). Independent variables in the study are drug dependence, life orientation, and job involvement, while the dependent variable is job performance.

Settings

The study was carried out at Ibadan, Oyo State command of Federal Road Safety Corps. Federal Road Safety Corps is the government agency. The Federal Road Safety Commission (FRSC) was established in 1988. The statutory functions include: making the highways safe for motorists and other road users, recommending works and infrastructures to eliminate or minimize accidents on the highways and educating motorists and members of the public on the importance of road discipline on the highways. Presently, the corps is statutorily established as a full-fledged Para-military outfit under the Federal Ministry of Interior. Structurally, organizational structure of the commission at the inception of the Commission, the Enabling Act of the Commission provides for the establishment of a governing council while the corps was headed by

a Director of organization and Chief Executive who oversees the day to day administration of the Corps. The structure of the commission has metamorphosed from six (6) directorates to eleven (11) departments in 2003 and finally down to eight (8) Departments as presently constituted with the nomenclature changing from directorates to departments. In the same vein, the number of sector commands has continued to increase in tandem with state creation. Today, the number of unit commands has grown from less than 20 in 1994 to 72 in 2005. For effective performance, the commission created a number of specialized units known as corps offices. These include the Public Education, Intelligence, Provost, Legal, Corps secretary, Audit and Corps protocol as well as Rescue which carry out specialized functions for the effective administration of the organization.

Participants

Members of Road Safety corps members serving within the Ibadan, Oyo State command with headquarters located at Eleyele, Ibadan, Oyo State were sampled in this study. Four hundred (400) FRSC officers were purposively selected as sample from the FRSC officers. 16.8% of the respondents were 25-30 years of age, 48.8% were 31-40 years, 28.5% were 41-50 years while 6.0% were 51 years of age. 56.8% of the respondents were male while 43.3% were female. 22.5% of the respondents were single, 74.3% were married, 1.3% were separated while 2.0% were divorced. 3.3% of the respondents had primary school certificate, 18.8% had secondary certificate, 17.3% had OND, 25.0% had HND, 24.5% acquired a university degree, 9.8% possess a master degree while 1.5% bagged a doctoral degree. 65.8% of the respondents had 1-10 years of experience, 29.5% had 11-20 years of experience while 4.8% had 21 years and above experience. 1.5% are in accounting department, 23.5% were in operations, 4.8% in PGC, 8.3% were in anti-fraud department, 1.0% were in department of technology, 3.8% in PRS, 6.0% in intelligence department, 1.0% in disasters, 7.8% in PCR department, 0.8% in Sport department, 0.8% in legal department, 4.8% were admin, 3.5% were technician, 5.5% were provost, 0.3% were civil servant, 0.3% works in public service, 0.5% works in transport department, 2.8% were in department of NHF, 6.5% were in A. squad, 2.3% were in crisis management, 8.3% were in department of A. Vand, 3.0% were in department of armed squad, 2.3% were in pension department while 1.3% were in training department.

Instrument

In this study, source of data was solely primary. The quantitative data was collected using a standardized questionnaire as the primary research instrument. Questionnaires are techniques of data collection in which each person is asked to respond to the same set of questions in a predetermined order (de Vaus, 2002). Items used were drawn from existing questionnaires because they were developed over a longer period, and have already been statistically analyzed and tested a number of times to ensure that the questions asked do indeed capture the essence of the constructs and can meet the objectives of the survey. The instrument was divided into five basic parts, viz; In order to describe the sample, the following general demographics were included in the survey; gender, age, length of employment, rank and income.

Life orientation

The 10-item Life Orientation Test – Revised (LOT-R; Scheier, Carver, & Bridges, 1994) was used to assess an individual's level of dispositional optimism. Individuals indicate expectations about the future by rating the extent to which they think their future outcomes will be good or bad using a 5-point Likert type scale anchored by strongly disagree (0) to strongly agree (4). The LOT-R was scored as measuring a unidimensional construct.

Job performance.

Job performance was measured using the in-role performance scale items developed by Williams and Anderson (1991). In each case, responses were given on a 5-point scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). High score on this measure indicates high job performance, while low scores indicate low job performance. The Cronbach's alpha for the in-role performance scale was .93. In this study, a reliability coefficient alpha of 0.90 was obtained.

Job involvement

Job involvement was measured by 12 items taken from the job involvement scale developed by Lodahl and Kejner (1965). Each item was measured on a five-point scale where a value of one corresponded to "Strongly Disagree" and a value of 5 corresponded to "Strongly Agree". The scores obtained on each of the

12 items were averaged to produce a single score for job involvement. Brown (1996) on the basis of his meta-analytic study contends that the job involvement scale developed by Lodahl and Kejner (1965) is a reliable and useful measure of job involvement and as a result this scale was utilized to measure the construct of job involvement in the present study. The value of coefficient alpha for this sample was 0.71.

Severity of Dependence Scale (SDS)

The Severity of Dependence Scale (SDS) is a 5-item questionnaire that provides a score indicating the severity of dependence on opioids. Each of the five items is scored on a 4-point scale (0-3). The total score is obtained through the addition of the 5-item ratings. The higher the score the higher the level of dependence. The SDS takes less than a minute to complete. The reliability coefficient alpha of 0.74 was obtained.

Procedure

Organizations were recruited through both personal contacts and a random sample from online searches and indirect contacts. Each potential organization was approached with a brief description of the study. Organizations in three area command to participate in the study and these are; Ibadan, Oyo State Central, Ibadan, Oyo State -west and Ibadan, Oyo State east. The research instruments were administered by hand for the purpose of better cooperation and ease in collection. The data gathering exercise was carried out within 8 weeks. Research assistants were employed to facilitate the process. 3 assistants with a minimum of school leaving certificate were recruited, and paid a fair fixed wage, with commission based on number of responses collected. The researcher explained to the respondents that the questionnaires were strictly for research purpose only. They were however assured that the information would be treated confidentially. Amidst the five hundred questionnaires that were distributed, 400 questionnaires were properly completed and therefore used for the data analysis.

Method of Data Analysis

The raw data collected using the structured questionnaire were sorted, edited, coded and reviewed so as to have the required quality, accuracy, consistency and completeness. It was then analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Scientists (SPSS) computer package to test the relationship of life orientation, substance dependence, job involvement and job performance. Demographic data were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as mean, range, standard deviation, percentages and standard deviation. All the four hypotheses stated were tested using inferential statistics of t-test for independent determine group differences, multiple regression analysis and Pearson correlation samples for relationship between at 0.05 level of significance.

Result

The first hypothesis stated that there will be significant relationship among drug dependence job involvement, life orientation and job performance of FRSC officers and men under the Oyo State command. This hypothesis was tested using Pearson correlation and the result presented in Table 4.1

Table 4.1: Zero order correlation showing the relationship between life orientation, job performance and drug dependence on job performance

Variables	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4
Job performance	24.63	5.19	-	.078	.176**	-.209**
Life orientation	36.45	7.94		-	.694**	.297**
Job involvement	26.25	5.53			-	.270**
Drug dependence	16.02	4.39				-

Table 4.1 shows that there was significant relationship between job involvement ($r=.18$, $p<0.01$), and drug dependence ($r=-.21$, $p<0.01$) significantly correlate job performance. While life orientation ($r=.08$, $p>0.05$) did not significantly correlate job performance. The result shows that increase in job involvement will

significantly increase job performance. Also, the result shows that increase in drug dependence will significantly decrease job performance. The hypothesis was accepted.

The second hypothesis stated that drug dependence job involvement, and life orientation will jointly and independently predict job performance of FRSC officers and men under the Oyo State command. This hypothesis was analysed using multiple regression analysis and the result presented in Table 4.2:

Table 4.2: Summary of Multiple Regression table showing joint and independent influence of life orientation, job performance and drug dependence on job performance

Predictors	β	t	P	R	R ²	F	P
Life orientation	-.026	-.390	> .05				
Job involvement	.268	4.033	<.05	.320	.102	15.041	< .05
Drug dependence	-.274	-5.469	<.05				

Table 4.2 shows that there was significant joint influence of life orientation, job involvement and drug dependence on job performance [F (3,396) = 15.04, R² = .102; p < .05] with the variables accounting for 10% of the variance in job performance. Further results show that job involvement (β =.27; p<.05) and drug dependence (β =-.27; p<.05) significantly predict job performance while life orientation (β =-.03; p>.05) did not significantly predict job performance. The hypothesis was accepted.

Female officers will significantly report higher job performance than male FRSC officers and men under the Oyo State command. This hypothesis was analysed using t-test for independent samples and the result presented in Table 4.3:

Table 4.3: Summary table of independent sample t-test showing the influence of gender on Job performance

DV	Gender	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t	p
Job performance	Male	227	24.72	5.18	398	0.411	>.05
	Female	173	24.50	5.20			

Table 4.3 shows that gender did not have significant influence on job performance (t= 0.41; df= 398; p>.05). This means that male respondents (X= 24.72; SD= 5.18) reported better job performance compare to female respondents (X= 24.50; SD= 5.20) who reported lesser job performance.

Age, years of experience and educational qualification will jointly and independently predict job performance among FRSC officers and men under the Oyo State command. This hypothesis was analysed using multiple regression analysis and he result presented in Table 4.4:

Table 4.4: Summary of Multiple Regression table showing joint and independent influence of age, years of experience and educational status on job performance

Predictors	β	t	P	R	R ²	F	p
Age	.088	1.437	> .05				
Years of Experience	-.027	-.447	>.05	.282	.079	11.364	< .05
Educational status	.245	4.580	<.05				

Table 4.8 shows that there was significant joint influence of age, years of experience and educational status on job performance [F(3,396) = 11.36, R² = .079; p < .05] with the variables accounting for 8% of the variance in job performance. Further results show that educational status (β =.25; p<.05) significantly predict job performance. While age (β =.09; p>.05), years of experience (β =-.03; p>.05) did not significantly predict job performance. The hypothesis was accepted.

Discussion

This chapter deals with the discussion of findings, conclusion and recommendations based on the findings of this study. Specifically, the study provided answers to four research hypotheses. Three hypotheses were confirmed and one was not supported. The discussion of the findings is presented in this chapter.

The first hypothesis stated that there will be significant relationship between drug dependence, job involvement, life orientation and job performance of FRSC officers and men under the Oyo State command was confirmed. There was significant relationship between job involvement and drug dependence significantly correlate job performance. While life orientation did not significantly correlate job performance. Based on the findings of the current study, it is possible to conclude that job involvement is associated with job performance. Moreover, this finding of the study is in line with previous studies which suggested that job performance is associated with job involvement (Johari & Yahya, 2016; Carmeli, 2005; Philip & Moberg, 2007). Absolutely these findings confirm those of previous studies relating drug abuse and job productivity of the employees at the workplace. Frone (2006); Lehman and Bennet (2002); Pryce (2008) drug abusers are less productive, miss work more often and are much more likely to file worker's compensation claims. Further, they are likely to have health problems that affect their productivity which in turn lead to personal problems and distract them from their jobs. The finding also supports the study of Bressler, et. al, (2010) and Kluemper, et al., (2009) which found that academic performance is positively associated with optimism. Green et al., (2004) found a significant relationship between optimism and performance in manufacturing settings.

The second hypothesis stated that drug dependence, job involvement, and life orientation will jointly and independently predict job performance of FRSC officers and men under the Oyo State command was significant. It was demonstrated that there was significant joint influence of life orientation, job involvement and drug dependence on job performance. Further results show that job involvement and drug dependence significantly predict job performance. This result of the study supports the second hypothesis of the study. Based on the findings of the current study, it is possible to conclude that job involvement is powerful predictor of job performance. Moreover, this finding of the study is in line with previous studies which suggested that job performance is predicted by the job involvement of employee (Johari & Yahya, 2016; Carmeli, 2005; Philip & Moberg, 2007). Absolutely these findings confirm those of previous studies relating drug abuse and job productivity of the employees at the workplace. The findings support the studies of Frone, (2006); Lehman and Bennet (2002); NIDA (2005) and CCHOS (2005), who demonstrated that drug abuse affect workplace conditions and level of productivity. CCHOS (2005) argue that drug abuse directly undermines productivity at the workplace and studies indicate that even consumption of fairly low quantities of drugs can lead to a relatively high loss in the level of productivity. Pryce (2008) add that drug abusers are less productive, miss work more often and are much more likely to file worker's compensation claims. Further, they are likely to have health problems that affect their productivity which in turn lead to personal problems and distract them from their jobs. The finding also agrees with studies that exist that academic performance is positively associated with optimism (Bressler, et. al, 2010; Kluemper, et al., 2009; Norem and Chang, 2002; Siddique, et al., 2006). Studies that have focused on the optimism-performance have primarily been in the sales literature (Dixon and Schertzer, 2005). Green et al., (2004) examined the relationship between optimism and performance in manufacturing settings.

The third hypothesis stated that female officers will significantly report higher job performance than male FRSC officers and men under the Oyo State command. That gender did not have significant influence on job performance. The finding supports the study of Anuar, et al (2009) who reported that gender did not have a significant impact on work performance. However, in contrast with Wiedmer, (2006) who found that gender was significantly related to organizational performance

The fourth hypothesis age, years of experience and educational qualification will jointly and independently predict job performance among FRSC officers and men under the Oyo State command was supported. Further results show that educational statuses significantly predict job performance. While age and years of experience did not significantly predict job performance. Education influences positively work performance (Linz, 2002). McBey and Karakowsky (2001) found causal relationship between education and work performance. In Pakistan; private educational institutions normally have a good name (Ardic & Bas, 2002). Khalid & Irshad (2010) found employees working in public sector institutions more satisfied with job security as compared to their matching part.

Conclusion

This study aims to investigate the role of drug dependence, job involvement, life orientation on job performance among staff of Federal Road Safety Corps. Considering the importance of the study, and of

course various results, this study concluded that there was significant relationship between job involvement, drug dependence and job performance. In addition, job involvement and drug dependence significantly predict job performance. Conversely, life orientation was insignificant of job performance. Similarly, gender did not have significant influence on job performance. Further, educational status significantly predict job performance. Overall, findings of the study suggested that job involvement and drug dependence play a vital role in determining the job performance of employees. This study is both theoretical and empirical significance. From the theoretical perspective, the results and findings are expected to contribute to HRM, and employee attitude and behavior literature. From the practical perspective, the researcher believes that results of this study will helpful to understand the importance of job involvement and drug dependence in improving job performance of employees among practitioners.

Recommendations

Given the findings stated above, the following recommendations are offered:

- Fostering high levels of job involvement among employees can be an effective strategy to increase both forms of performance and to foster more positive attitudes and behaviours. Therefore, investing in conditions, which help to make employees more involved in their jobs, is likely to be important for the growth and profitability of the organizations.
- In addition, management should develop applying several innovative practices and initiatives to enhance the job involvement of officers resulting in improved job performance, as highly involved employees always have positive mindset and attitude towards their job and organization which encourage them to perform in a way to reach the organizational goals and objectives.
- Management should provide psychosocial intervention, given the roles of life orientation and drug dependence in predicting job performance.
- There is need for management to have capacity development programmes to sensitize their officers/employees across the board and increase their awareness of the adverse consequences of drug use, especially in an organisation whose success depends on the safety of Nigerians.
- There is a need for the government and the larger society to control availability and access to drugs.
- Given the critical role the sector, employee's mannerism and behaviour and the need for face-to-face interaction with the clients, there is a need for the road safety sector to put in place stringent policy mechanisms to curb drug use and/or abuse among its officers, as this would go a long way to minimize the risk of drug and alcohol consumption that cause professional invalidity and incapacitated employees.
- Lastly, officer's demographic factors should be given priority in their recruitment and selection process.

Limitations and Directions for Future Research

While interpreting the results, the current study has a few limitations that are worthy to mention, and that should be addressed by forthcoming researchers. The sample is regional and signifies only road safety sector. Again, this study ignores the mediating effects of job involvement in on the relationship between drug dependence and job performance. In addition, the findings of this study are only based on the information from FRSC in Ibadan Oyo State, Nigeria, which may limit the degree to which the findings can be generalized to other settings. Moreover, the findings of this study are methodologically limited by restrictions imposed by the study in specific industry, which not permit the generalization of findings. The current study is a cross-sectional study.

Therefore, it is important for future studies to validate the current findings in a longitudinal design could be more appropriate than cross-sectional ones for establishing casual inferences based on preexisting theory and empirical data (Chiaburu et al., 2010). The current study only applies a quantitative research design. Therefore, future studies may consider collecting deeper data from the respondents. The use of both qualitative and quantitative methods would provide an opportunity for more depth and richer explanations regarding the relationships among drug dependence, job involvement and job performance. Future studies should consider the antecedent variables related to this study.

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